

second week of Oct was accompanied by high wind velocity. We assessed the loss in yield among cultivars of different maturity groups.

Maximum yield loss was 55% in IET7251 — the crop lodged 1 wk before flowering — followed by Sugandha, which lodged at booting (see table). Among the semidwarfs, maximum yield loss was in Radha that lodged 1 wk before flowering, followed by Pankaj that lodged either at flowering or at booting. Minimum yield loss was in Sujata that lodged 10 d after flowering. □

Effect of time of lodging on rice yields.

Variety	Duration (d)	Growth stage at lodging	Yield (t/ha)		Loss ^a (%)
			Lodged	No lodging	
<i>Dwarf (high yielding varieties)</i>					
Pankaj	155-160	Booting	3.5	6.5	46.8 e
Pankaj	155-160	Flowering	3.5	6.7	47.4 e
Radha	155-155	1 wk before flowering	3.1	6.2	49.9 f
Radha	150-155	1 wk after flowering	4.7	6.1	23.6 b
Sujata (BG90-2)	135-140	At flowering	3.5	5.4	35.7 c
Sujata (BG90-2)	135-140	10 d after flowering	4.4	5.2	18.2 a
Sita	135-140	1 wk after flowering	3.2	5.4	41.0 d
Sita	135-140	2 wk after flowering	3.2	5.4	41.6 d
<i>Tall plant type</i>					
Sugandha	Photoperiod sensitive	Booting	1.5	3.3	54.3 g
ET7251	155-160	1 wk before flowering	2.2	4.8	55.1 g

^a Values followed by identical letters are not significantly different from each other at the 5% level.

Seed dormancy in some short-duration rices

C. Kundu, A. Ghosh, and R. Ghosh, Rice Research Station, Chinsurah, India

We assessed seed dormancy in 11 traditional rice varieties and 14 promising short-duration (90-110 d) breeding lines grown during aus (Mar-Sep), when preharvest seed sprouting in the field often follows monsoon rains. Seeds collected 30 d after flowering, coinciding with peak monsoon months, were dried to 13-14% moisture content. Germination at harvest and length and intensity of dormancy were measured. Dormancy intensity was determined by the time necessary to break dormancy with 50 °C heat treatment for 4 d. Dormancy length was days to attain 80% germination under ambient conditions.

Dormancy was 15-44 d in the traditional varieties and 27-54 d in the breeding lines. Many traditional varieties had strong seed dormancy; all the breeding lines except CR289-1208

Seed dormancy of 25 shortduration rices. Chinsurah, India.

	Germination (%) after 4 d heat treatment at 50° C	Dormancy	
		Intensity ^a	Period (d)
<i>Traditional</i>			
Bhutmuri	24	MD	30
Harimandir	nil	SD	40
Orissa aus	2	SD	40
Begunbichi	2	SD	42
Soni	78	WD	43
Panke	nil	SD	32
N22	2	SD	35
Baumal	32	MD	31
Joli	nil	SD	44
Juma	98	WD	41
China aus	100	WD	15
<i>Breeding lines</i>			
HPU741	74	WD	42
IR9708-51-1-2	72	WD	35
IR9729-67-3	88	WD	40
CR289-1208 (IET7255)	55	MD	54
Suweon	100	WD	28
BKNLR75091-CNT-B3 RST40-2-2	100	WD	37
IR8608-189-2-2-1-3	95	WD	30
Pusa 312	100	WD	38
OR165-93-15	78	WD	44
RP2086-74-6-1	100	WD	27
UPLRi7	90	WD	27
IR13204-24-16	90	WD	34
NSRP-1 Early	95	WD	30
RAU4045-10	85	WD	33

^a WD = weakly dormant, MD = moderately dormant, SD = strongly dormant.

(IET7255) were weakly dormant (see table). China aus attained 100%

germination after heat treatment and had very weak dormancy. □

Leaf chlorophyll content of submerged rice seedlings

S. Gupta, P. Sengupta, and B. Banerji, Rice Research Station, Chinsurah 712102, Hooghly, West Bengal, India

We assessed leaf chlorophyll content of seedlings of six rice varieties (B-9c-Md-3-3, CN540, CR126-42-1, FR13A, Mohon, and OC1393) grown in pots under submerged and nonsubmerged conditions.

Seedlings were raised in 25-cm-diam earthen pots at 50 seeds/pot with 8 replications. At 10 d after seeding (DAS), 4 pots/variety were submerged in 50-cm water for 10 d, then treated normally to 35 DAS. Leaf chlorophyll

content was estimated at 10, 12, 16, 20, 24, and 35 DAS.

Leaf chlorophyll content decreased with increasing age of seedlings (see table). Chlorophyll content in submerged seedlings was similar to that in nonsubmerged seedlings up to 6 d after submersion, then dropped drastically. After submersion ended, chlorophyll content continued to decrease for 4 d before recovery started.

B-9c-Md-3-3 had the highest chlorophyll content after submergence.

Chlorophyll content of leaves of submerged and nonsubmerged rice seedlings. West Bengal, India.

Variety	Chlorophyll content (mg/g fresh wt) of seedlings at given days after seeding										
	Nonsubmerged						Submerged			Recovery	
	10	12	16	20	24	35	12	16	20	24	35
B-9c-Md-3-3	2.16	2.14	1.92	1.87	1.84	1.73	2.84	1.43	1.58	0.46	2.27
CN540	5.12	1.73	2.64	1.98	2.13	2.13	2.68	1.92	0.46	0.77	–
CR126-42-1	3.50	2.55	1.95	1.73	1.56	1.43	3.80	1.54	1.30	0.62	–
FR13A	2.91	3.01	1.20	1.22	1.70	1.70	2.65	1.92	0.73	0.17	2.39
Mohon	3.21	3.73	2.37	2.19	1.67	0.94	5.03	2.10	0.64	0.57	–
OC1393	4.32	3.88	2.86	2.16	2.04	1.70	4.28	1.81	0.71	1.10	2.27
Mean	3.54	2.84	2.06	1.86	1.82	1.61	3.55	1.79	0.91	0.62	2.31

CN540 seedlings had the highest chlorophyll content at 10 DAS, but

content decreased faster with aging. Three varieties died. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization GRAIN QUALITY

Grain quality of new varieties PR 108 and PR 109 in Punjab, India

S.K. Uppal and G.S. Sidhu, Punjab Agricultural University, Regional Rice Research Station, Kapurthala, India

Two new rice varieties were released in Punjab in 1986. PR108 is resistant to sheath blight and whitebacked planthopper (WBPH), PR109 is resistant to bacterial blight and

WBPH. PR108 and PR109 are as high yielding as PR103 and PR106 and Jaya under disease- and insect-free conditions (see table).

Total rice recovery and head rice recovery of PR108 and PR109 equaled those of PR103, PR106, and PR4141 and head rice recovery was higher than Jaya's.

The new varieties have long, slender white grains. PR108 has high and PR 109 has intermediate amylose

content. Cooking quality compares favorably with that of PR106, PR4141, PR103, and Jaya. PR108 and PR109 have slightly higher protein content than other varieties.

With their good milling quality, desirable appearance, good cooking and eating quality, and good protein value, the new varieties are likely to be as acceptable to consumers and millers as PR106, which commands a premium price. □

Grain quality characteristics of rice varieties.^a Kapurthala, India.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)	Total rice recovery (%)	Head rice recovery (%)	1,000-grain wt (g)		Length: breadth ratio	Cooking time (min)	Kernel elongation ratio	Volume expansion ratio	Amylose (%/dry basis)	Protein (%) at 14% moisture
				Paddy	Milled rice						
PR108	7.1	74.0	63.1	23.3	17.3	3.2	19	1.8	4.2	26.2	8.0
PR109	6.9	73.0	63.0	24.5	18.8	3.2	26	1.7	4.8	24.7	8.7
PR103	6.6	73.3	63.3	25.0	18.9	3.0	19	1.6	3.7	16.0	7.9
PR106	6.5	73.5	63.2	22.8	16.9	3.3	18	1.8	3.9	25.4	7.8
Jaya	7.1	75.2	56.6	27.3	21.6	2.5	22	1.7	4.2	26.3	7.8
PR4141	5.8	74.2	61.3	21.9	16.5	3.0	23	1.7	4.6	23.1	7.9

^aAv of 3 replications.

Relationship of agroclimatic parameters to high density grain production

S. P. Rao, Directorate of Rice Research, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 500030, A. P., India

Production of high density (HD) grains differs with crop duration, season, and N levels. We found that HD grain index (% of fully filled grain at 1.18 specific gravity divided by spikelets per panicle) is influenced

positively by crop duration and season and negatively by N level.

Long-duration varieties IET5656, Mahsuri, CR 1009, and Pankaj had higher HD grain indexes than the short- and medium-duration varieties